

Emotional Intelligence of Adolescents in Relation to Gender and Area of Residence

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Abstract— The main purpose of this research is to study the emotional intelligence of adolescence with regards to their gender and area of residence. For the present research 50 male urban adolescence, 50 male rural male adolescence, 50 female urban adolescence and 50 female rural adolescence were randomly selected from the urban and rural area of the Ahmedabad city. Emotional Intelligence Scale by A. K. Singh and Shruti Narain was used for data collection. To analyzed the data 't' test was used Results indicate that Significant difference was found between male and female adolescences with regards to their emotional intelligence. Female adolescences have better Emotional Intelligence than male adolescences. Significant difference was found between urban and rural adolescences with regards to their emotional intelligence. Rural adolescences have better Emotional Intelligence than urban adolescences. Significant difference was found between urban male and urban female adolescences with regards to their emotional intelligence. Urban female adolescences have better Emotional Intelligence than urban male adolescences. Significant difference was found between rural male and rural female adolescences with regards to their emotional intelligence. Rural female adolescences have better Emotional Intelligence than rural male adolescences.

I. INTRODUCTION

World Health Organisation (WHO) defines an adolescent as any person between the ages of 10 and 19. This development phase is marked by the onset of puberty, the emergence of more advanced cognitive abilities, and the transition into new roles in society.

Adolescences, according to Bass and Ball (1960), is the "transition stage from childhood to maturity, during which new patterns of behaviour must be developed to meet the demands both of the larger and more diverse, such as his peers, and of the adult society which he begins to enter."

According to Erikson's (1963), adolescences is characterized as a developmental stage wherein individuals engage in a quest for ego identity, as they strive to define and understand themselves. If the individual achieves success, they will gain a proper understanding of time, develop a healthy sense of self-esteem, assume the role of an experimenter and leader/follower in a balanced manner, and establish strong ideological commitments.

The word "Emotion" originates from the Latin word "EMOVERE," which can indicate "movement," "stir up," or "agitate. Another way to think about emotion is as "e-motion," or the drive that inspires us. Different emotional states have varying energy levels. It has long been believed that intellect belongs in the brain, and emotions reside in the heart. Therefore, emotional intelligence is the result of the brain and heart working together to promote emotional empowerment and ultimately lead to self-actualization.

Mayer and Salovey (1993) define emotional intelligence as the capacity to effectively observe and regulate one's own and others' emotions, discerning between different emotional states, and utilizing this knowledge to inform one's cognitive processes and behavior's. This definition encompasses the notion that emotional intelligence encompasses both interpersonal and intrapersonal talents. Interpersonal skills encompass the capacity to comprehend and acknowledge the emotions of others, demonstrate empathy, foster and cultivate interpersonal connections, and exhibit a heightened sense of social responsibility, which is particularly emphasized. Intrapersonal abilities, on the other hand, encompass the capacity to comprehend and interpret one's own motivations.

Daniel (1995), emotional intelligence can be described as the cognitive ability to identify and comprehend both our own emotions and the emotions of others, which in turn enables us to effectively motivate ourselves within the context of interpersonal connections.

According to Goleman, emotional intelligence can be defined as the capacity to recognize, evaluate, and manage one's own emotions, as well as the emotions of others and those within collective settings. The individual in question has established a conceptual framework consisting of five distinct aspects that serve to delineate the construct of emotional intelligence.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Sarika (2018). “Researcher aimed to study emotional intelligence and its impact on adjustment of tribal students of high school in Dadar and Nagar haveli. The result says there’s no significant difference between male and female high school students related to emotional intelligence. Whereas, results says that rural high school students are emotionally stronger compare to urban students.

Venishya (2018). “The purpose of the study was to understand the relationship between parenting styles and level of emotional intelligence of higher secondary school children. The major findings revealed that there’s positive relationship of parenting styles on emotional intelligence of the higher secondary school children. There’s significant difference seen in the emotional intelligence of children and education level of the head of the family. Whereas, there’s no statistically significant difference seen in gender though their difference in means in gender for emotional intelligence. Also, there’s no significant difference between income group of family members and emotional intelligence of children”.

Adelina et al. (2021) “The goal of doing this research was to know the emotional intelligence and parenting style among late adolescences. Research was conducted on 129 participants between 18yrs-24yrs and results revealed that no significant gender difference among late adolescences between emotional intelligence and parenting style whereas there was significant relationship in perceived mother and father autonomy with emotional intelligence”.

Dr Amardeep. (2017) “The current study is to understand the relationship between Perceived Parenting and emotional Intelligence of early Adolescents. The total samples were 500 (250 females, 250 males.250 urban and 250 rural and 250 rural) adolescents chosen randomly from Mukstar District. K-S test was used to check the normality of the data. The result indicated the significance difference between Emotional Intelligence and authoritative perceived parenting style in male and female adolescents. The result also says that there’ significant difference between emotional intelligence and authoritarian an authoritative perceived parenting style of urban adolescents whereas significant relationship between emotional intelligence and authoritative perceived parenting style of rural adolescents”.

EI. Tahra M. Elmaghraby. (2022) “Many studies are been done and still been examined to understand the psychological and sociopsychological elements of emotional Intelligence on adolescences and late adolescences, The purpose of this research was to explore the prediction of perceived parenting styles in childhood to emotional intelligence as ability in late adolescences. The total sample size was 177 and selected from Cairo University. The administration was done on basis of socialization inventory and modified Emotional intelligence as ability scale. The result says that perceived father tolerance predicted in EI in male whereas mother acceptance predicted EI in females.”

III. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

The main purpose of the present research is to study and compare Emotional Intelligence of Adolescences with regards to their gender and area of residence. The exact problem of the present research is “Emotional Intelligence of Adolescences in relation to Gender and area of residence”.

III.I. OBJECTIVES

- (1) To study and compare Emotional Intelligence of male and female adolescences.
- (2) To study and compare Emotional Intelligence of urban and rural adolescences.
- (3) To study and compare Emotional Intelligence of male urban adolescences and female urban adolescences.
- (4) To study and compare Emotional Intelligence of male rural adolescences and female rural adolescences.

III.II. HYPOTHESIS

H₀₁ There is no significant difference between male and female adolescences with regards to Emotional Intelligence.

H₀₂ There is no significant difference between urban and rural adolescences with regards to Emotional Intelligence.

H₀₃ There is no significant difference between male urban and female urban adolescences with regards to Emotional Intelligence.

H₀₄ There is no significant difference between male rural and female rural adolescences with regards to Emotional Intelligence.

IV. SAMPLE OF THE STUDY

For the present research 200 adolescences were randomly selected from the difference High schools of Urban and Rural area of Ahmedabad District. Total sample was categorized as under :

	Male	Female	Total
Urban	50	50	100
Rural	50	50	100
Total	100	100	200

V. VARIABLES

In present research Gender and Area of residence of adolescences are taken as independent variables and scores of Emotional Intelligence is taken as dependent variables.

VI. TOOLS

Emotional Intelligence scale by A. K. Singh and Shruti Narain

Following four dimensions were included in constructing this scale. Their brief description is given below :

- (a) Understanding emotions – An individual’s capacity to identify emotions in one’s and other’s physical states, feelings, and thoughts.
- (b) Understanding motivation – A high achievement drive together with the tendency to be optimistic and take initiative.
- (c) Empathy – Ability to identify oneself mentally with others and to understand a person or thing accurately and read how other people feel, understand their perspectives, develop others, leverage diversity, read the mood of a group, discern political realities and a tendency to take an interest in the lives of others.
- (d) Handling relations – To be able to manage and handle relations with others in a better way.

This Emotional intelligence Scale is meant for use from 12 years and above of age.

VI.I. RELIABILITY

The test re-test reliability was calculated, by administrating the test on the same sample (N=100) with a gap of fortnight. it was found to be 0.86 alpha coefficients, which was significant at .01 level.

VI.II. VALIDITY

The present scale was correlated against the Emotional Intelligence Scale developed by Hyde, Pethe and Dhar (2001). The concurrent validity was found to be 0.86, which was significant at .01 level. For this purpose, both scales had been administered on the same sample (N=100).

VI.III. SCORING

The answers of those items which tallied with the answers given in the scoring key were given a score of +1. If they didn’t tally, they were given a score of zero. The scoring key is provided in Table.

Table : Scoring Table

Sr. No.	Dimensions	Items	Serial wise Items No.	Total	
I.	Understanding emotions	Positive	5, 15, 18, 28	4	4
		Negative	---	--	
II.	Understanding Motivation	Positive	3, 7, 9, 12, 16, 19	6	8
		Negative	20, 21	2	
III.	Empathy	Positive	6, 8, 10, 23, 25, 26, 29, 31	8	10
		Negative	13, 17	2	

IV.	Handing relations	Positive	1, 2, 4, 11, 14, 22, 24, 27, 30	9	9	
		Negative		--		
Positive 27 + Negative 4 =				Total		31

VII. PROCEDURE

After establishing the rapport with randomly selected adolescences from various high school of urban and rural areas of Ahmedabad district. Instructions were given regarding responses for data collection of Emotional intelligence Scale by Arunkumar Singh. Emotional intelligence scale was administered in small manageable group of adolescences. After completion of data collection scoring was done with the help of manual of each scale.

VIII. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

To analyzed data mean, SD and t was used.

Table : 1
Mean, SD and t value of Emotional Intelligence of
Male and Female adolescences

Group	N	Mean	SD	t	Leve of Significance
Male adolescences	100	22.87	4.11	2.05	Significant 0.05
Female adolescences	100	23.90	3.22		

The result of table no. 1 shows the t value of emotional intelligence of male and female adolescences is 2.05 which is significant at 0.05 level. So, the null hypothesis, “There is no significant difference between male and female adolescences with regards to emotional intelligence” is rejected. Mean scores of male adolescences on emotional intelligence are 22.87 and mean scores of female adolescences on emotional intelligence is 23.90 with SD 4.11 and 3.22 respectively. It means significant difference was found between male and female adolescences with regards to their emotional intelligence. Female adolescences have better Emotional Intelligence than male adolescences.

Table : 2
Mean, SD and t value of Emotional Intelligence of
Urban and Rural adolescences

Group	N	Mean	SD	t	Leve of Significance
Urban adolescences	100	21.88	3.82	2.19	0.05
Rural adolescences	100	22.91	3.17		

The result of table no. 2 shows the t value of emotional intelligence of male and female adolescences is 2.19 which is significant at 0.05 level. So, the null hypothesis, “There is no significant difference between Urban and Rural adolescences with regards to emotional intelligence” is rejected. Mean scores of urban adolescences on emotional intelligence are 21.88 and mean scores of rural adolescences on emotional intelligence is 22.91 with SD 3.82 and 3.17 respectively. It means significant difference was found between urban and rural adolescences with regards to their emotional intelligence. Rural adolescences have better Emotional Intelligence than urban adolescences.

Table : 3
Mean, SD and t value of Emotional Intelligence of
Urban Male and Urban Female adolescences

Group	N	Mean	SD	t	Leve of Significance
Urban Male Adolescences	50	10.23	1.73	2.28	0.05
Urban Female adolescences	50	10.96	2.03		

The result of table no. 3 shows the t value of emotional intelligence of urban male and female adolescences is 2.28 which is significant at 0.05 level. So, the null hypothesis, “There is no significant difference between Urban Male and Urban Female adolescences with regards to emotional intelligence” is rejected. Mean scores of urban male adolescences on emotional intelligence are 10.23 and mean scores of urban female adolescences on emotional intelligence is 10.96 with SD 1.73 and 2.03 respectively. It means significant difference was found between urban male and urban female adolescences with regards to their emotional intelligence. Urban female adolescences have better Emotional Intelligence than urban male adolescences.

Table : 4
Mean, SD and t value of Emotional Intelligence of
Rural Male and Rural Female adolescences

Group	N	Mean	SD	t	Leve of Significance
Rural Male Adolescences	50	10.94	1.91	4.34	0.01
Rural Female adolescences	50	12.96	1.59		

The result of table no. 4 shows the t value of emotional intelligence of rural male and female adolescences is 4.34 which is significant at 0.01 level. So, the null hypothesis, “There is no significant difference between Rural Male and Rural Female adolescences with regards to emotional intelligence” is rejected. Mean scores of rural male adolescences on emotional intelligence are 10.94 and mean scores of rural female adolescences on emotional intelligence is 12.96 with SD 1.91 and 1.59 respectively. It means significant difference was found between rural male and rural female adolescences with regards to their emotional intelligence. Rural female adolescences have better Emotional Intelligence than rural male adolescences.

IX. CONCLUSIONS

1. Significant difference was found between male and female adolescences with regards to their emotional intelligence. Female adolescences have better Emotional Intelligence than male adolescences.
2. Significant difference was found between urban and rural adolescences with regards to their emotional intelligence. Rural adolescences have better Emotional Intelligence than urban adolescences.
3. Significant difference was found between urban male and urban female adolescences with regards to their emotional intelligence. Urban female adolescences have better Emotional Intelligence than urban male adolescences.
4. Significant difference was found between rural male and rural female adolescences with regards to their emotional intelligence. Rural female adolescences have better Emotional Intelligence than rural male adolescences.

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